

RASAVAHA SROTAS: AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE ON PHYSIOLOGY,
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ABSTRACT

Aim: This study aims to explore the comprehensive concept of *Rasavaha Srotas*, focusing on their physiological significance, etiopathogenesis, and therapeutic management as described in classical *Ayurveda*. **Materials and Methods:** Classical *Ayurvedic* texts, including *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, were thoroughly reviewed to extract detailed references on *Rasa Dhatu* and *Rasavaha Srotas*. Relevant modern sources, such as journals and scholarly articles, were consulted to correlate classical descriptions with contemporary physiological understanding. **Results/Findings:** *Rasavaha Srotas* serve as primary channels for the formation and distribution of *Rasa Dhatu*, the first dhatu responsible for nourishment of all subsequent tissues. The *Moolasthan* at *Hridaya* and distribution via *Dhamanis* mirror the cardiovascular and lymphatic systems. Vitiating of these channels (*Rasavaha Srotodushti*) due to improper diet, excessive unctuous food, cold intake, or psychological stress leads to *Sanga* (obstruction), *Kha Vaigunya* (structural defects), impaired *Rasa* circulation, and systemic manifestations, including digestive disturbances, pallor, lethargy, premature aging, and increased susceptibility to metabolic and cardiovascular disorders. **Conclusion:** Management through *Langhana*, *Panchakarma*, dietary regulation, exercise, and *Nidana Parivarjana* restores proper circulation, strengthens *Agni*, removes *Ama*, and maintains homeostasis. Understanding *Rasavaha Srotas* is crucial for promoting health, preventing lifestyle-related disorders, and applying *Ayurveda*'s integrative, preventive, and curative principles in modern healthcare.

KEYWORDS: *Srotas*, *Ayurveda*, *Rasavaha Srotas*, *Srotodushti*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is the most ancient science of life, emphasizing both the prevention and treatment of diseases. Its fundamental principle is "Prevention is better than cure." *Maharshi Charaka*, in the 5th chapter of *Vimanasthana*, described the concept of *Srotas* and defined them as channels through which the transforming *Dhatu*s (*Parinamapadhyamana Dhatu*) are transported from one place to another.^[1] He further explained them as "*Sravanat Srotansi*", meaning structures through which the process of *Sravana* (flow) occurs.^[2] These channels transport temporary *Dhatu*s to be converted into permanent ones and also carry *Prana* (vital energy), *Udaka* (water), *Anna* (food), and three types of *Mala* (waste products).

Maharshi Sushruta, in the 9th chapter of *Sharira Sthana*, described *Srotas* as hollow channels, other than *Sira* and *Dhamani*, which arise from their root sites, spread throughout the body, and carry specific substances.^[3] After the action of *Jatharagni*, *Bhutagni*, and *Dhatvagni* on food, the *Poshya Dhatu* (nutritive essence) is formed,

which requires *Srotas* for distribution to every cell of the body. *Chakrapani* clarified that "*Sravanat*" indicates the flow of *Rasa* and other nutritive *dhatu*s, and thus, *Srotas* are defined as channels responsible for the regular conduction of nutrients for nourishment and *dhatu* formation.^[4]

Maharshi Vagbhata compared *Srotas* to the fine passages and pores within a lotus stem, through which *Rasadi Poshya Dhatu* circulates throughout the body, providing nutrition.^[5] The digested food ultimately forms *Rasa Dhatu*, the first *dhatu*, whose primary function is *Preenana* (nourishment). *Rasavaha Srotas* are the channels that carry *Rasa Dhatu* and nourish both *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*s.

In modern times, faulty lifestyle choices and unhealthy practices are significant contributors to *Srotodushti* (vitiating of channels of circulation), which leads to the development and progression of various diseases.

Rasa Samvahana (Circulation of Rasa)

Vyana Vayu, which has the inherent capacity to move fluids rapidly, is responsible for the circulation of *Rasa Dhatu* throughout the entire body.^[6]

Moolasthanas of Rasavaha Srotas

- According to *Charaka – Hridaya* (heart) and *Dasha Dhamanis* (ten great vessels).
- According to *Sushruta – Hridaya* and *Rasavahi Dhamanis*.

Thus, the *Moola* (root) of *Rasavaha Srotas* is the heart and great vessels. The *Marga* (pathway) corresponds to the venous and lymphatic systems, while the *Mukha* (opening) is represented by the arteriolar-venous junctions in the capillaries.

Rasavaha Srotas are considered the primary channels since they transport nutrients to all parts of the body and provide nourishment to both *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*. The *Moolasthanas* of *Rasavaha Srotas* is the *Hridaya*, and the *Sanchara Sthana* is the *Dasha Dhamanis/Rasavahi Dhamanis*.

The *Hridaya*, located in the middle mediastinum of the thoracic cavity, functions as the central organ that pumps blood along with *Rasa Dhatu* continuously throughout the body. It acts both as a storage site and a pumping unit for *Rasa Dhatu*. The *Dasha Dhamanis* then transport the subtle nutritive essence of properly digested food, i.e., *Rasa Dhatu*, to every part of the body. Hence, the *Hridaya* is regarded as the *Moolasthanas* from the storage perspective, while the *Dasha Dhamanis* are considered the *Moolasthanas* from the conduction perspective.

Types and Moola Sthana of Srotas by Charaka and Sushruta

Sr. No.	Name Of Srotas	Acharya Charaka ^[9]	Acharya Sushruta ^[10]
1	<i>Pranavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Hridaya, MahaSrotas</i>	<i>Hridaya, Rasavahini Dhamani</i>
2	<i>Udakavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Talu, Kloma</i>	<i>Talu, Kloma</i>
3	<i>Annavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Aamashaya, Vamaparshva</i>	<i>Aamashaya, AnnvahiniDhamani</i>
4	<i>Rasavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Hridaya, 10Dhamani</i>	<i>Hridaya, Rasavahini Dhamani</i>
5	<i>Raktavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Yakrita, Pleeha</i>	<i>Yakrita, Pleeha and RaktavahiniDhamani</i>
6	<i>Mamsavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Snayu, Twaka</i>	<i>Snayu, Twaka and RaktavahiniDhamani</i>
7	<i>Medovaha Srotas</i>	<i>Vrikka, Vapavahana</i>	<i>Kati, Vrikka</i>
8	<i>Asthivaha Srotas</i>	<i>Meda, Jaghana Pradesha</i>	-
9	<i>Majjavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Asthi, Sandhi</i>	-
10	<i>Shukravaha Srotas</i>	<i>Vrishana, Shepha</i>	<i>Stana, Vrishana</i>
11	<i>Mutravaha Srotas</i>	<i>Vasti, Vankshana</i>	<i>Vasti, Medhra</i>
12	<i>Purishavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Pakwashaya, Sthulaguda</i>	<i>Pakwashaya, Guda</i>
13	<i>Swedavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Meda, Looma Koopa</i>	-
14	<i>Artavavaha Srotas</i>		<i>Garbhashaya, ArtavavahiniDhamani</i>

AIM

The aim of this study is to explore the comprehensive concept of *Rasavaha Srotas*, with special emphasis on their physiological significance and therapeutic management as explained in *Ayurveda*.

The process of *Agni* and *Panchabhautika Agni* acting on food results in the formation of *Ahara Rasa*. Further transformation by *Rasadhatvagni* converts this into *Sarabhuta Rasa Dhatu*. *Rasa Dhatu* then circulates in the body with the help of *Vyana Vayu*, propelled through the *Hridaya*.

If “*Kha Vaigunya*” (structural defects) occur in the *Rasavaha Srotas*, obstruction of *Rasa Dhatu (Sanga)* results, which ultimately leads to *Roga/Vikriti* (disease manifestation). Any abnormality in the formation or nutrition of *Rasa Dhatu* adversely affects the nourishment of *Hridaya Moola* and *Rakta Dhatu*. According to the principle of *Kshiradadhi Nyaya*, *Rasa Dhatu* nourishes the subsequent *Dhatu*; hence, its disturbance affects the entire *Dhatu* formation chain.

Properties of Rasa Dhatu

As described – “*Raso’Pi Shleshmavat*”^[7], *Rasa Dhatu* possesses properties similar to *Kapha Dosha*, such as being *Snigdha* (unctuous), *Guru* (heavy), and *Shweta* (whitish).

Number of Srotas

The statement “*Yavantah Purushe Murtimanto Bhavavisheshatavanta Evasmin Srotasam Prakar Visheshah*” indicates that the *Srotas* are innumerable, as every constituent of the body has its own channel.^[8] *Acharya Charaka* described 13 types of *Srotas*, whereas *Maharshi Sushruta* mentioned 11 types of *Yogavahi Srotas*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Classical *Ayurvedic* texts, including the *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, were thoroughly reviewed for references related to the concept of *Rasa Dhatu* and *Rasavaha Srotas*.

2. Relevant modern sources such as journals, research papers, and scholarly articles were also examined to support and correlate the classical understanding.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Rasavaha Srotas Dushti Hetu (Etiological Factors)^[11]

The classical texts describe several causative factors responsible for the vitiation of *Rasavaha Srotas*:

- **Guru Ahara (Heavy diet):** Excessive intake of heavy foods such as cheese, fast food, bakery items, and certain processed foods.
- **Sheeta Ahara (Cold food):** Frequent consumption of excessively cold food and beverages.
- **Ati-Snigdha Ahara (Over-unctuous food):** Intake of excessively oily or fatty foods, which increase the viscosity of blood, obstruct circulation, and create blockages in the channels.
- **Samashana (Improper dietetic habits):** Consumption of wholesome and unwholesome food items together.
- **Manasika Hetu (Psychological causes):** Excessive stress and *Ati-Chinta* (worry) lead to vitiation of *Rasavaha Srotas*, resulting in conditions such as

hypertension, cardiac disorders, and impaired mental as well as physical health.

Rasavaha Srotas Dushti Lakshana/Roga (Clinical Manifestations)^[12]

The signs and symptoms of *Rasavaha Srotas* vitiation include:

- Loss of appetite and disinterest in food (*Ashraddha, Aruchi*)
- Altered taste perception (*Aasyavairasyam*)
- Lack of relish for food (*Arasajnyata*)
- Nausea, heaviness, and lethargy (*Hrillasa, Gaurava, Tandra*)
- Body ache, fever, and breathlessness (*Saangamarda, Jwara, Tama*)
- Pallor (*Pandutva*)
- Obstruction of channels (*Strotorodha*)
- Impotency and weakness (*Klaibya, Saada*)
- Emaciation (*Krishangata*)
- Impairment of digestive fire (*Agni-nasha*)
- Premature wrinkling and graying of hair (*Ayathakaala Vali-Palata*).

Diseases Due to *Rasa Dhatu* Imbalance (*Charaka*)

1	<i>Ashraddha</i>	Disinclinations for any type of food
2	<i>Aruchi</i>	Anorexia or uninterested diet
3	<i>Aasyavairasya</i>	Dysgeusia
4	<i>Arasangayata</i>	Ageusia or loss of taste
5	<i>Hrilaso</i>	Nausea
6	<i>Gaurav</i>	Feeling heaviness
7	<i>Tandra</i>	Drowsiness
8	<i>Saangamarda</i>	Bodyache
9	<i>Jwara</i>	Fever
10	<i>Tama</i>	Darkness in front of eyes
11	<i>Pandu</i>	Anaemia
12	<i>Strotasaam rodha</i>	Obstruction of channels of circulation
13	<i>Klaibya</i>	Impotency
14	<i>Saada</i>	Asthenia/weakness
15	<i>Krishangata</i>	Emaciation
16	<i>Nashoagneya</i>	Decrease power of digestion
17	<i>Vali and paalitya</i>	Premature appearance of wrinkles and grey hairs

Physiological Importance of *Rasavaha Srotas*^[13,14]

The *Acharyas* emphasized that the integrity of *Srotas* is the basis of life processes in both health and disease.

- *Srotas* serve as channels for the transport of *Dhatu*s (tissues or their components) and for their transformation into stable forms.
- They conduct both *Prasada Dhatu* (nutritive essence) and *Mala Dhatu* (waste products), contributing to the formation of *Sthayi Dhatu* (permanent tissues).
- Beyond being mere pathways, each *Srotas* has distinct functions, ensuring nourishment to respective *Dhatu*s in proper quantity, without excess.

- They act as the body's internal transport system, supporting the activities of *Doshas, Dhatu*s, *Ojas, Agni*, thoughts, and emotions.
- *Rasavaha Srotas* specifically aid in fat and mineral absorption through the lymphatic system and utilize circulatory pressure for distribution.
- They serve as the site for transformation of *Ahara Rasa* into *Rasa Dhatu* and provide pathways for its transportation throughout the body.
- Proper functioning of *Rasavaha Srotas* contributes to the excellence of the *Twak* (skin), reflected by qualities such as *Shlakshna* (smoothness), *Mridu* (softness), *Prasanna* (clarity), *Sukshma* (fineness), and *Sukumara* (delicacy).

- Normal physiology of *Rasavaha Srotas* ensures happiness, vitality, intellect, enjoyment, and longevity.
- These channels play an essential role in maintaining body temperature regulation.
- Digestion and assimilation of food are facilitated by biochemical processes of *Rasa*, which are distributed through *Rasavaha Srotas*.
- They also contribute to immune response, supporting healing and defense mechanisms at the site of injury.

CHIKITSA (Management of *Rasavaha Srotodushti*)

Acharya Charaka prescribed the treatment for disorders arising from the vitiation of *Rasa Dhatu* as: “*Rasajaanaam Vikaaranaam Sarva Langhanam Aushadham*”.^[15] This means that for the management of all diseases caused by vitiated *Rasa Dhatu*, *Langhana* (fasting or lightening therapies) is considered the foremost line of treatment. Since *Rasavaha Srotas* are the channels carrying *Rasa Dhatu*, their vitiation essentially implies the vitiation of *Rasa Dhatu* itself. As *Rasa* is the first *Dhatu*, its impairment leads to the disturbance of all subsequent six *Dhatu*s and their respective *Srotas*. Thus, the treatment of *Rasavaha Srotodushti* is crucial to prevent further *Dhatu* and *Srotas* vitiation.

Charaka further clarifies the interrelation of *Dhatu*s and *Srotas*: “*Tesham (Srotas) Prakopaat Sthanastha Cha Eva Maargaga Cha Sharirdhaatvah Prakopamapadyante*”.^[16] This highlights that the vitiation of *Srotas* directly results in the vitiation of *Dhatu*s; therefore, therapies targeting *Dhatu*s are equally effective in correcting *Srotodushti*.

The primary causes of *Rasavaha Srotodushti* are *Agnimandya* (weak digestive fire) and *Ama* (toxic undigested material). Hence, *Langhana* is the first line of management. *Langhana* is the foremost therapy among the *Shat Upakrama* (six treatment modalities), intended to lighten the body and relieve heaviness.

According to Charaka, the types of *Langhana* are described as:

“*Chatusprakara Samsuddhih, Pipasa Marutatapau; Pacananya Upavasasca Vyayamas Ceti Langhanam*”.^[17]

Types of *Langhana*

1. *Vamana* – Therapeutic emesis
2. *Virechana* – Therapeutic purgation
3. *Niruha Basti* – Decoction enema
4. *Nasya* – Nasal administration of cleansing medicines
5. *Pipasa* – Control of thirst
6. *Maruta* – Exposure to air
7. *Atapa* – Exposure to sunlight
8. *Pachana* – Use of *Ushna Virya* (hot potency) foods and medicines to improve digestion
9. *Upavasa* – Complete fasting
10. *Vyayama* – Physical exercise

All these forms of *Langhana* act primarily by enhancing digestive and metabolic power (*Agnibala*).

Indications for *Panchakarma Therapy*^[18]

- Recommended for the elimination of excessively vitiated *Doshas* (*Bahudoshavastha*).
- Indicated when both the disease and the patient’s strength are strong.

Indications for *Pachana Therapy*^[19]

- Suitable for moderate diseases (*Madhya Bala Roga*).
- Recommended when *Doshas* are moderately vitiated.

Indications for Control of Thirst and Fasting^[20]

- Applied in mild diseases where *Doshas* are not severely vitiated.
- Helps restore *Doshic* balance by controlling hunger and thirst.

Indications for Exercise, Sun, and Wind Exposure^[21]

- Beneficial for strong individuals suffering from mild ailments.
- Physical exercise and exposure to sun and air help restore normal physiology.

Signs of Adequate *Langhana*^[22]

- Proper elimination of urine, stool, and flatus.
- A feeling of lightness in the body.
- Cleansing effect in belching, heart, mouth, and throat.
- Disappearance of fatigue and drowsiness.
- Appearance of perspiration.

Overall, *Langhana* therapy is employed whenever there is a sense of heaviness. Along with lightening the body, it also enhances *Deepana* and *Pachana* (digestive and metabolic capacity).

Nidana Parivarjana (Avoidance of Causative Factors)

A fundamental principle of *Ayurvedic* treatment is *Nidana Parivarjana*, which emphasizes the avoidance of etiological factors responsible for disease. It focuses on correcting dietary habits and lifestyle modifications that contribute to the onset of *Rasavaha Srotodushti*. Consuming wholesome, balanced food and adopting a healthy lifestyle are considered the most effective preventive strategies.

DISCUSSION

The concept of *Rasavaha Srotas* holds a central position in *Ayurvedic* physiology as it governs the transportation of *Rasa Dhatu*, the first and most vital tissue responsible for nourishment and sustenance of the entire body. Acharyas like Charaka, Sushruta, and Vagbhata described the *Moolasthanas* of *Rasavaha Srotas* as the *Hridaya* and *Dhamanis*, which closely parallels the heart, blood vessels, and lymphatic pathways in modern science. This reflects *Ayurveda*’s advanced

understanding of circulation and nutrient transport centuries before modern discoveries.

The *Hetu* (causative factors) of *Rasavaha Srotodushti*, such as heavy diet, oily food, improper combinations, and mental stress, bear striking similarity to contemporary risk factors of hypertension, dyslipidemia, and cardiovascular diseases. Likewise, clinical features like anorexia, lethargy, pallor, impaired digestion, and premature aging indicate systemic consequences of disturbed *Rasa* circulation. The *Ayurvedic* concepts of *Sanga* (obstruction) and *Kha Vaigunya* (structural defect) resonate with modern pathological mechanisms of atherosclerosis and nutritional deficiency.

Physiologically, *Rasavaha Srotas* not only transport nutrients but also regulate immunity, mental stability, and skin health. This aligns with modern recognition of circulation in maintaining systemic homeostasis and microcirculatory function.

Management primarily emphasizes correction of *Agnimandya* and elimination of *Ama*, with *Langhana* (lightening therapies) as the foremost line of treatment. *Panchakarma*, fasting, exercise, and lifestyle regulation restore balance by enhancing digestion and metabolism. Furthermore, *Nidana Parivarjana* underscores the importance of preventive strategies, advocating wholesome food, mental calmness, and healthy routines—principles that parallel modern lifestyle medicine.

Thus, *Rasavaha Srotas* offer an integrative model where *Ayurvedic* wisdom complements modern physiology, highlighting their significance in prevention and management of lifestyle disorders.

CONCLUSION

Rasavaha Srotas occupy a pivotal role in *Ayurvedic* physiology, acting as the primary channels for the circulation of *Rasa Dhatu*, the first and foundational tissue responsible for nourishment and sustenance of all subsequent *Dhatu*s. The *Moolasthanas* at *Hridaya* and the distribution via *Dhamanis* emphasize the sophisticated understanding of nutrient transport and circulatory dynamics in classical *Ayurveda*, which parallels modern concepts of the cardiovascular and lymphatic systems. Vitiating of these channels, caused by improper diet, excessive unctuous food, cold intake, stress, or lifestyle factors, disrupts the formation and distribution of *Rasa Dhatu*, ultimately affecting systemic health and predisposing to metabolic, cardiovascular, and immunological disorders.

Management of *Rasavaha Srotodushti* through *Langhana*, *Panchakarma*, dietary regulation, physical exercise, and *Nidana Parivarjana* not only restores proper circulation and nutrient flow but also strengthens *Agni* and removes *Ama*, thereby maintaining homeostasis. The principles underscore the

interconnectedness of *Dhatu*s and *Srotas*, highlighting that correction at the primary level prevents downstream disturbances.

In conclusion, *Rasavaha Srotas* exemplify the integrative approach of *Ayurveda*, linking structural, functional, and preventive aspects of health. Understanding and maintaining their integrity is crucial for overall well-being, longevity, and prevention of lifestyle-related disorders, reinforcing *Ayurveda*'s timeless wisdom in both curative and prophylactic healthcare.

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